

Computational Study of the Application of Al_2O_3 Nanofluids in Forced Convection of High-Reynolds Swirling Jets for Engineering Cooling Processes

F.-J. Granados-Ortiz^a, L. Leon-Prieto^b, J. Ortega-Casanova^b

^a Department of Mathematical Sciences, University of Greenwich, Park Row, London SE10 9LS, UK

^b Escuela de Ingenierías Industriales. Andalucía Tech. Universidad de Málaga

Abstract

In this paper the application of nanofluids for high-Reynolds turbulent jet flows for heat transfer in cooling processes is simulated. Six volume fractions have been investigated ($\phi = 0, 2, 4, 6, 8$ and 10% , which means a Prandtl number of the nanofluid within the range $Pr_{nf} \in [7, 14.4]$) along with two nozzle-to-plate distances ($H/D = 2$ and 4) and three swirl numbers ($S = 0, 0.45$ and 0.83). The jet regime is fixed at a Reynolds number $Re = 35000$. The computational study shows that the application of nanoparticles enhance forced convection for all the simulations carried out. However, the influence of swirl number and nozzle-to-plate distance is not that clear, causing different effects on the performance, leading even to vortex breakdown for high swirl numbers, which affects to heat transfer. Correlations dependent on H/D , Pr_{nf} and S are also given for the area-weighted averaged and stagnation Nusselt number, as well as the standard deviation of the radial Nusselt profile as measure of the cooling distribution uniformity, of strong importance in engineering processes such as tempering of glasses to obtain a high quality product.

Keywords: CFD, Cooling jet, nanofluid, turbulent flow, mathematical correlations

1. Introduction

In heat transfer applications, impinging jets are a popular mechanism for cooling heated surfaces [1] and frequent examples of their use are cooling electronic devices

Figure 1: Impinging jet zones. Reprinted from [12] with permission.

4 [2], cooling in industrial machining processes [3], glass tempering [4, 5, 6], cooling of
 5 windshields of vehicles [7] or when the temperature of irradiated targets must be reduced
 6 [8], amongst many others. The complex nature of a turbulent impinging jet flow makes
 7 further work necessary to evaluate and predict the characteristics of heat transfer [9].
 8 Initial research in this field dates back to 1951, with the experimental approach carried
 9 out by Freidman and Mueller [10], and to 1953, when Kenzios combined theory and
 10 experiments in his doctoral thesis [11]. Since then, the jet flow is normally divided
 11 into three regions: free jet region, stagnation region and wall jet region respectively, as
 12 shown in Fig. 1. Thus, an improvement of the cooling in the stagnation region and a
 13 radial distribution of the heat transfer along the wall jet region is generally desired.

14 Numerous authors have studied which parameters influence this heat transfer mech-
 15 anism. As early as in 1966, Gardon and Akfirat [13] analyzed the influence of the
 16 nozzle-to-plate distance, concluding that the maximum heat transfer in the stagnation
 17 region is reached at a nozzle-to-plate distance of approximately six times the diameter.
 18 Average heat transfer, while inside of the potential core, was shown to be essentially
 19 independent of the nozzle-to-plate spacing, as reported by Hrycak [14]. When the jet
 20 is tilted, the point of maximum heat transfer shifts from the geometrical impingement
 21 point towards the compression side of the plate. The scaled shift of maximum heat
 22 transfer increases with a decreasing the oblique angle (more inclination of the jet). The
 23 shift is found to be sensitive for smaller jet-to-plate distance [9, 15]. To model turbu-
 24 lence in these configurations is complex as most turbulence models are developed for

25 parallel flow to the plate, as evidenced in [16].

26 The impinging jet considered in the present paper is turbulent. The existence of
27 turbulence in wall jets is, in fact, recommendable since the radial Nusselt distribution
28 strongly depends on this feature, as shown by several authors [17, 18, 19]. These
29 authors explicitly outlined the presence of secondary peaks in the Nusselt profile due
30 to the transition to turbulent flow.

31 Swirling flows have been a hot-topic line of research for decades [20]. Depending
32 on the swirl mechanism, swirl intensity definition can be based on geometrical or ve-
33 locity considerations. For instance, the swirl number can be defined as the ratio of
34 the azimuthal characteristic velocity to the axial characteristic velocity. Experimental
35 studies have established that swirl has large scale favorable effects on various aspects
36 of jet flows, such as spreading jet growth and instabilities, flow entrainment and de-
37 cay [21], leading to an increase of heat transfer because of rotation [22]. Visualization
38 techniques applied in [23] showed that heat transfer rates of the moderate swirling jets
39 ($S = 0.4$) are found to enhance the non-swirling jet performance, whereas those of
40 larger swirl numbers ($S = 0.78$ and 0.94) are diminished compared to the non-swirling
41 jet. This is due to momentum distribution of the jets before impingement. The most
42 relevant phenomenon when dealing with swirling flows is vortex breakdown. At low
43 swirl level ($S \lesssim 0.6$ [20]), there may be significant radial pressure gradients at any axial
44 position due to centrifugal effects, but these do not lead to axial recirculation. There
45 is no coupling between the axial and tangential velocity components. When substan-
46 tially increasing the swirl, a strong coupling takes place between axial and tangential
47 velocity components. A point is reached, when the adverse pressure gradient along the
48 jet axis cannot be further overcome by the kinetic energy of the fluid particles flowing
49 in the axial direction, and a recirculation flow appears in the central portion of the jet.
50 Leibovich [24] describes a vortex breakdown as “a disturbance characterized by the for-
51 mation of an internal stagnation point on the vortex axis, followed by reversed flow in
52 a region of limited axial extent”. Although this rupture occurs in numerous forms, two
53 of them predominate: one called “nearly-axisymmetric” (in the form of a bubble), and

54 another called “spiral”. Vortex breakdown may occur in turbulent swirling jet flows.
55 Actually, for Burger’s vortex and depending on both the value of the vortex core radius
56 δ and the Reynolds number Re , there is a critical swirl number, $S = S^*(\delta, Re)$, above
57 which recirculating vortex breakdown bubbles are observed in the near axis region [25].

58 Regarding the working fluid, this can be also improved in order to increase heat
59 transfer. Maxwell was the first to develop a theoretical model for the thermal conduc-
60 tivity of a suspension of spherical particles, estimating that the improvement of this
61 property would be more pronounced with the increase of the volume fraction of parti-
62 cles and the relation between the area and the volume of the same [26]. Hamilton and
63 Crosser [27] simplified the model, by providing correlations that made it possible to ob-
64 tain the thermal conductivity of the mixture according to the properties of the original
65 materials, the composition of the mixture and the shape of the particles. From this,
66 other simpler models were developed, such as the one given by Wasp [28]. However, due
67 to the large size and high density of the particles, there was no good way to prevent the
68 solid particles from settling out of suspension. The lack of stability of such suspensions,
69 induced additional flow resistance and possible erosion [29]. In 1995, Choi [30] pro-
70 posed that the particles should be of nanometric size. By applying the Hamilton and
71 Crosser correlation, Choi obtained a significant improvement in heat transfer, reducing
72 the power required by the heat exchanger pumps [30]. In this same work, the term
73 “nanofluids” was introduced to refer to the new highly conductive refrigerant resulting
74 from the addition of nanometric particles in fluids such as water, ethylene glycol or
75 oil, which revolutionized the concept proposed by Maxwell more than 100 years earlier.
76 Although Choi’s model was theoretical, Eastman’s experimental results [31] and Lee’s
77 ones [32] were in accordance with the theoretical predictions. Specifically, Eastman
78 obtained a heat transfer improvement of 60% with a volume fraction of only 5%. While
79 these conclusions may seem promising, the development of the field is hindered by the
80 lack of agreement between results obtained in different laboratories, the often poor
81 characterization of the suspensions and the lack of theoretical understanding of the
82 mechanisms responsible for the observed changes in properties [33]. Some papers argue

83 that the answer to this last question lies in analysing the behaviour of nanofluids on a
84 microscopic scale [34, 35]. Brownian motion, thermal diffusion [36] or liquid-solid inter-
85 face [37, 38] have been taken into account, attributing to this layer the great change in
86 thermal conductivity. There is not yet a contrasted universal model to jointly account
87 all these phenomena. However, the multiphase model, which separately analyzes the
88 solid particles and the fluid considering that each phase has a separate velocity vector
89 and temperature field, seems to be gaining relevance [39]. On the other hand, the lower
90 complexity implicit in simulating a monophasic model, in which nanofluid is considered
91 as a homogeneous fluid, is the most used in computational research in the field, yielding
92 accurate results [40, 41].

93 Nanoparticles have been applied to impinging jet flows for heat transfer in several
94 works in the literature. For instance, in [42], different experiments were conducted by
95 using SiO_2 nanofluid up to 8.5% solid volume fraction, and it was observed that the
96 Nusselt number increased with the volume fraction and Reynolds number. Addition-
97 ally, in [43], the effect of different nanofluids (TiO_2 , Al_2O_3 and SiO_2) and different
98 concentrations are tested experimentally for a laminar single jet. This investigation
99 concludes that they behave similarly at the same concentration, possibly because the
100 same size of the particles, and also that the use of nanofluids enhances heat transfer
101 in comparison to water jets. In [44] a Cu-water nanofluid is tested experimentally and
102 their results show a remarkable increase in the heat transfer coefficient of the base fluid
103 when using nanofluids. Similarly, in [45] Cu nanofluids are applied to heat transfer in a
104 single impinging jet, by testing in this experimental work different jet angles, flow rates,
105 nozzle shapes, nozzle-to-plate distances and concentration of nanoparticles. This study
106 reports that the use of Cu nanofluids enhance heat transfer, specially for orthogonal
107 jets, whilst pressure drop is not remarkably affected. In [46], TiO_2 -water and water-
108 multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT-water) nanofluids are applied to the study
109 their boiling heat transfer aspects by means of laminar jets. Again, it is observed that
110 nanofluids enhance the cooling process. Also, it is reported that the vapor film stability
111 may be affected by the presence of nanoparticles, which leads to a shift in the boiling

112 curve of the regime. In [47], swirling jets with CuO nanofluid are applied in experi-
 113 ments to increase heat transfer by impingement with different CuO concentrations. The
 114 Reynolds numbers considered range between 1600 and 9400, and the swirl is added to
 115 the flow by means of twisted tapes. These investigations encourage the objective of the
 116 present work, where the application of a swirling/non-swirling jet flow at high Reynolds
 117 number regime, with different Al_2O_3 nanoparticle concentrations, swirl intensities and
 118 nozzle-to-plate distances is numerically studied as an efficient cooling application.

119 After this Introduction, the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, the compu-
 120 tational domain, together with the governing equations, boundary conditions, output
 121 parameters and thermophysical properties of the nanofluid are described. Next, in
 122 Section 3, some numerical considerations are given, such as the validation with exper-
 123 imental results and a grid convergence study. After this section, Section 4 is devoted
 124 to present and discuss all the results found. Finally, in Section 5 the conclusions are
 125 given.

126 2. Formulation of the problem

Figure 2: Sketch of the problem to study.

127 When modeling a symmetric circular swirling turbulent jet, which is impinging
 128 against a solid flat plate with diameter $8D$ (being D the diameter of the jet), it is
 129 usually efficient and accurate to consider azimuthal symmetry of the geometry and

130 boundary conditions (axisymmetric problem), as discussed in [18]. This means that
 131 the study can be developed in a bi-dimensional (2D) plane $r - z$. A 2D section of the
 132 domain, which is also the computational domain, can be seen in Fig. 2. This depicts
 133 the impingement of the flow at a known distance H to the plate. The flow is a nanofluid
 134 with constant density ρ_{nf} and viscosity μ_{nf} (nf stands for nanofluid throughout the
 135 paper). Therefore, considering the axisymmetric, turbulent, steady, and incompressible
 136 jet flow, the motion of the fluid is governed by the continuity, momentum and energy
 137 equations, which in compact notation can be written as

$$\frac{\partial V_i}{\partial x_i} = 0; \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(V_i V_j)}{\partial x_j} = & \\ & - \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\nu_{nf}}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\frac{\partial V_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial V_j}{\partial x_i} - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \frac{\partial V_l}{\partial x_l} \right] \\ & + \frac{\partial(-v'_i v'_j)}{\partial x_j}; \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

138

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} [V_i(\rho e + P)] = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[K_{eff} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \right], \quad (3)$$

139 where V_i with $i = z, r, \theta$ are the axial, radial and azimuthal average velocity components,
 140 whereas P , T and e are the pressure, temperature and internal energy per unit mass,
 141 respectively. Additionally, δ_{ij} is the Dirac's delta, K_{nf} is the thermal conductivity,
 142 $K_{eff} = K_{nf} + K_t$ is the effective thermal conductivity, K_t is the turbulent thermal
 143 conductivity $K_t = c_{p,nf} \mu_t / Pr_t$, c_p is the fluid heat capacity, μ_t is the turbulent dynamic
 144 viscosity and Pr_t is the turbulent Prandtl number. In ANSYS-Fluent© the default
 145 value is $Pr_t = 0.85$, whose value can be tuned in the turbulent model if necessary. On
 146 the other hand, v'_i are the unknown velocity component fluctuations. To solve these,
 147 closure equations are necessary. This problem closure is completed by using a turbulent
 148 model. In the present work, The Shear Stress Transport (SST) $k - \omega$ model is used,
 149 and the two closure equations in compact notation for k (turbulent kinetic energy) and

150 ω (specific turbulent dissipation rate) respectively are:

$$\rho_{nf} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (kV_i) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\Gamma_k \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right) + G_k - Y_k, \quad (4)$$

151

$$\rho_{nf} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\omega V_i) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\Gamma_\omega \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \right) + G_\omega - Y_\omega, \quad (5)$$

152 where Γ_k and Γ_ω are the effective diffusivity of k and ω , while G_k and G_ω are the
 153 generation of k and ω , respectively, due to mean velocity gradients. Finally, Y_k and Y_ω
 154 are the dissipation of k and ω , respectively. Further information on their definition and
 155 implementation can be found in [48].

156 For the sake of formality, Eqs. (1)-(5) can be made dimensionless. To that end,
 157 the pipe diameter D is used as characteristic length, the axial average velocity of the
 158 impinging jet U_c as characteristic velocity, D/U_c as characteristic (convective) time
 159 and $\rho_{nf} U_c^2$ as characteristic pressure, with ρ_{nf} being the density of the fluid, μ_{nf} its
 160 viscosity and $\nu_{nf} = \mu_{nf}/\rho_{nf}$ its kinematic viscosity. The Reynolds number is thus
 161 defined as $Re = U_c D/\nu_{nf}$, which is kept constant throughout this work ($Re = 35000$).
 162 The molecular Prandtl number is defined as $Pr = c_{p,nf} \mu_{nf}/K_{nf}$. As aforementioned,
 163 the fluid density and viscosity are considered constant since the flow is incompressible,
 164 but dependent on the concentration of nanoparticles. The dimensionless distance H
 165 from the plate to the nozzle has been fixed to $H/D = 4$.

166 To quantify the efficacy of the cooling of the surface, the ratio of the heat transfer
 167 by forced convection and conduction, namely Nusselt number, is defined as:

$$Nu = \frac{h_c D}{K_{nf}}, \quad (6)$$

168 where h_c is the convective heat transfer coefficient. Specially relevant is the Nusselt
 169 number at the stagnation point ($Nu_0 \equiv Nu(r = 0)$), and the area-weighted average
 170 Nusselt number (\overline{Nu}), defined as

$$\overline{Nu} = \frac{1}{A} \int_A Nu dA = \frac{1}{A} \sum_{i=1}^n Nu_i |A_i|, \quad (7)$$

171 with Nu_i the Nusselt number at the i -th element on the plate grid, A_i the area of the
 172 i -th element, and A the total area.

173 The uniformity of the heat transfer is an important observation that defines the
 174 performance of the cooling configuration. To that end, the uniformity is evaluated by
 175 means of the standard deviation of the Nusselt number distribution:

$$\sigma = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{A} \left(\int_A \sum_{i=1}^n (Nu_i - \overline{Nu}) dA \right)}}{\overline{Nu}}. \quad (8)$$

176 Theoretically, if $Nu(r) \simeq \text{constant}$, $\sigma \simeq 0$. Thus, the lower the σ , the more uniform
 177 the cooling by forced convection. This is a relevant feature for the quality of certain
 178 cooling applications, such as tempering of glasses [4, 5, 6].

179 Since the flow is a swirling and non-swirling jet flow in this work, the swirl intensity
 180 must be formally quantified. This parameter is usually defined as the ratio of the
 181 azimuthal bulk velocity (V_b) over the axial bulk velocity:

$$S = \frac{V_b}{U_b}, \quad (9)$$

182 with

$$V_b = \frac{2}{(D/2)^2} \int_0^{D/2} \hat{r} \hat{V}_\theta dr \text{ and } U_b = \frac{2}{(D/2)^2} \int_0^{D/2} \hat{r} \hat{V}_z dr, \quad (10)$$

183 being averaged velocities at the jet exit section [49].

184 When modelling the variation of the thermophysical properties of a nanofluid, with
 185 water as base fluid and aggregation of nanoparticles of Al_2O_3 in the present application,
 186 a single phase or homogeneous model can be used [50]. This assumes that the liquid
 187 phase and nanoparticles are in thermal equilibrium and moving at the same velocity.
 188 In this case, the effective density of the nanofluid can be modelled by the well-known
 189 two phase mixture as

$$\rho_{nf} = (1 - \phi)\rho_{bf} + \phi\rho_p, \quad (11)$$

190 where ρ_{bf} is the base fluid density (water), ϕ is the volume fraction of nanoparticles
 191 and ρ_p is the density of the solid particles in the nanofluid. Thus, the subscripts bf ,
 192 nf and p denote the base fluid, nanofluid and nanoparticle, respectively. Additionally,
 193 under thermal equilibrium conditions, the specific heat of nanofluid is given by

$$C_{nf} = (1 - \phi)C_{bf} + \phi C_p. \quad (12)$$

Figure 3: Axial and azimuthal velocity profiles at inlet boundary for $\phi = 0\%$ (water) and $S = 0.45$ [49].

194 The dynamic viscosity μ_{nf} of the nanofluid is computed by using the least squares curve
 195 fitting correlation on experimental data given by [51]:

$$\mu_{nf} = \mu_{bf}(123\phi^2 + 7.3\phi + 1). \quad (13)$$

196 Finally, the thermal conductivity of the nanofluid K_{nf} is obtained by using the well-
 197 known Hamilton and Crosser model [27]:

$$K_{nf} = K_{bf}(4.97\phi^2 + 2.72\phi + 1). \quad (14)$$

198 The thermophysical properties of both base fluid and nanoparticles are shown in Table
 199 1.

200 Finally, according with all this thermophysical properties, the Prandtl number of
 201 the nanofluid flow can be evaluated as

$$Pr_{nf} = \frac{C_{nf}\mu_{nf}}{K_{nf}} = \frac{[\mu_{bf}(123\phi^2 + 7.3\phi + 1)] [(1 - \phi)C_{bf} + \phi C_p]}{K_{bf}(4.97\phi^2 + 2.72\phi + 1)}, \quad (15)$$

202 which can be simplified and finally written as

$$Pr_{nf} = Pr_{bf} \frac{(123\phi^2 + 7.3\phi + 1)((1 - \phi) + \phi\beta)}{4.97\phi^2 + 2.72\phi + 1}, \quad (16)$$

Physical property	Water (<i>bf</i>)	Al_2O_3 (<i>p</i>)
ρ (kg/m ³)	998,2	3880
C (J/kg-K)	4182	773
K (W/m-K)	0,597	36
μ (Pa s)	993×10^{-6}	-

Table 1: Thermophysical properties of nanofluid’s components.

203 where β is the specific heat ratio, i.e. $\beta = C_p/C_{bf} \simeq 0.185$, and Pr_{bf} is the base fluid
204 Prandtl number, i.e. $Pr_{bf} = C_{nf}\mu_{nf}/K_{nf} \simeq 7$. To conclude, it is worth mentioning
205 that when $\phi \in [0, 10]\%$, then $Pr_{nf} \in [7, 14.4]$.

206 3. Numerical Considerations

207 Regarding the boundary conditions (see Fig. 2), the jet is modeled as a velocity-
208 inlet condition, whose axial and azimuthal velocity components are those obtained
209 experimentally in [49]. An example of both profiles is depicted in Fig. 3. For different
210 values of the volume fraction, the thermophysical fluid properties vary, and thus the
211 characteristic velocity U_c , in order to get the same Reynolds number throughout the
212 study: $Re = 35000$. For a full description of the boundary conditions, the symmetry
213 axis is located at the left-hand side of the domain to coincide with the nozzle centreline,
214 and the plate is located at the bottom, modelled as no-slip heated wall with an imposed
215 heat flux q . The boundary at the right-hand side and the upper boundary from the
216 edge of the nozzle till the end of the plate are pressure-outlet at atmospheric pressure.

217 The turbulent model used in the CFD simulation of the impinging jet flow is the
218 SST $k - \omega$, which has been previously used with satisfactory results by several authors
219 in impinging swirling/non-swirling jet flows for heat transfer, see e.g. [52, 53, 18, 1, 54],
220 among others. In addition, it has been conducted a validation test by comparing the
221 Nusselt profile distribution provided by our simulation with data from Lee et al. [55],
222 and Baughn & Shimizu [56]. Specifically, the simulated performance for that purpose
223 is a non-swirling ($S = 0$) air ($\phi = 0$) jet with $Re = 23000$ and impinging against the

224 heated plate located at $H/D = 2$. The comparison depicted in Fig.4 shows that the
 225 present work agrees quite well with data reported by previous authors, including the
 226 location and intensity of the secondary peak. This validates not only the turbulent
 227 model, but also the imposed boundary conditions and numerical discretisation schemes
 228 used in this study.

Figure 4: Validation of the CFD model for $Re = 23000$ and $H/D = 2$. Present work vs. Lee et al. [55], and Baughn & Shimizu [56] (5% error bars are also included).

229 For the sake of rigor, a second validation has been carried out for $Re = 35000$, since
 230 the numerical results provided in the next sections are under this Reynolds number
 231 regime. In this case, a both thermal and momentum validation has been carried out,
 232 by means of the Nusselt radial and pressure coefficient distribution, respectively. The
 233 comparison is shown in Fig. 5, where one can see that the current numerical results
 234 agree accurately with those provided in [49], for the pressure coefficient, and [57], for
 235 the normalized radial profile of the Nusselt number. By means of this validation is
 236 shown that the CFD simulation models accurately the mechanical and thermal reality
 237 of the problem.

238 In this section also a discretisation error analysis is carried out. For this purpose,

Figure 5: Validation of the CFD model for $Re = 35000$ and $H/D = 2$ in comparison with [49] and [57].

239 the CFD problem has been solved using four different meshes, with increasing number
 240 of grid cells, so that one can study how a quantity of interest varies along with the
 241 amount of cells. When by refining the mesh the variation in the quantity of interest is
 242 negligible, the grid convergence is achieved (in practice). Actually, a reliable reference
 243 value for comparison is obtained by Richardson’s Extrapolation (which would be the
 244 value for infinite cells). To that end of quantifying the discretisation error, the Grid
 245 Convergence Index (denoted as GCI hereinafter), is used following the methodology
 246 proposed by Roache [58]. In our case, the representative parameter is the total number
 247 of grid cells N_{total} , and the refinement ratio can be defined as $r = N_i/N_{i+1}$ (with N_i
 248 the number of cells of each mesh), which is kept almost constant. The second-order
 249 numerical methods used in this study imply a formal accuracy of $p_f = 2$, whereas the
 250 observed accuracy is $p_o = 6.28$, using the area-weighted average Nusselt number as
 251 quantity of interest, see Eq. (7). This shows that the accuracy obtained in this study is
 252 actually greater than the expected one corresponding to the second order discretization
 253 schemes employed. The GCI results are presented both in Table 2 and in Fig. 6, where
 254 one can see that the coarse mesh (with around 120 thousand cells) is the optimal one
 255 since the $GCI_{4,3}$ is small enough to consider the results of high reliability.

i	Grid	N_z	N_{total}	r_i	\overline{Nu}	$\text{CGI}_{i+1,i}$
1	Fine	650	195951	≈ 1.3	91.445	0.003 %
2	Medium	500	150801	≈ 1.3	91.440	0.014 %
3	Coarse	400	120701	≈ 1.3	91.414	0.05 %
4	Very coarse	300	90601	—	91.321	—

Table 2: Grid convergence study results.

Figure 6: Grid convergence study

256 It is relevant to point out from the mesh quality side that, in each mesh above con-
257 sidered, the distance of the first cell next to the flat plate wall is such that y^+ parameter
258 remains approximately equals to unity, in order to properly solve the boundary layer
259 and the heat transfer from the plate to the jet flow.

260 4. Results

261 The aim of this section is to investigate and discuss the results of the cooling pro-
262 cess by forced convection, quantified by means of the area-weighted averaged (\overline{Nu}) and
263 stagnation (Nu_0) Nusselt number, as well as its standard deviation (σ) in order to
264 quantify the uniformity of the transfer. To that end, it has been simulated the imping-
265 ing jet with six different volume fractions of nanoparticles, three swirl numbers and

266 two nozzle-to-plate distances. A summary of the obtained results for the three above
267 mentioned output parameters is shown in Fig. 7.

268 For the smallest nozzle-to-plate distance, $H/D = 2$, the area-weighted averaged
269 Nusselt number (\overline{Nu}) increases as the swirl number is increased, see Fig. 7 (a). This is
270 due to the fact that the swirl enhances turbulence and mixing, as explained in [53]. This
271 effect is shown in the present simulations as in Fig. 8, left column, where turbulence
272 intensity contours are shown. One can see that \overline{Nu} increases as swirl increases. On
273 the contrary, for $H/D = 4$, \overline{Nu} values are lower than for the short nozzle-to-plate
274 distance with $S > 0$. However, its value is greater for $S = 0$ when $H/D = 4$ rather
275 than $H/D = 2$, because of the large separation allows the jet turbulence to increase
276 and thus the heat transfer, see contours levels of Fig. 8 (a) and (b). Actually, when
277 the swirl number is increased, our results agree with those reported in [53], where a
278 transition is observed at $S = 0.45$. Additionally, the experimental approach described
279 in [23] led to equivalent results. In [53] this feature is attributed to the more evident jet
280 flow widening when impinging from a higher distance. This increase in the spreading
281 angle is sensitive to the swirl generator used in [53], as also pointed out in [18].

282 Regarding the Nusselt number at the stagnation point, Fig. 7 (b) illustrates differ-
283 ent trends. Regardless the nozzle-to-plate separation, it decreases as the swirl number
284 increases. This is because centrifugal forces spread the jet radially, thus preventing it
285 from impinging directly on the center of the plate and reducing the heat transfer on that
286 area. Velocity magnitude contours depicted in Fig. 9 illustrate this phenomenon, show-
287 ing that the low velocity region around the stagnation point grows radially outwards as
288 the swirl number increases. In contrast, Nu_0 increases as the nozzle-to-plate distance
289 increases. In Fig. 9 one can also see that the low velocity region becomes smaller when
290 the jet impinges from a higher distance. This result also agrees with those given in [53],
291 where it is pointed out that this is because at shorter nozzle-to-plate distances, the jet
292 deviates radially at a greater distance from the plate, which prevents it from efficiently
293 hitting the center of the plate. In addition, when the swirl intensity reaches $S = 0.83$
294 and regardless the nozzle-to-plate separation, a breakdown bubble occurs, see Fig. 9

(a) \overline{Nu} results

(b) Nu_0 results

(c) σ results

Figure 7: Heat transfer results. Solid and dashed lines represent quadratic fitting of the numerical data.

Figure 8: Turbulent intensity contours for $\phi = 8\%$.

(a) $S = 0$; $H/D = 2$.

(b) $S = 0$; $H/D = 4$.

(c) $S = 0.45$; $H/D = 2$.

(d) $S = 0.45$; $H/D = 4$.

(e) $S = 0.83$; $H/D = 2$.

(f) $S = 0.83$; $H/D = 4$.

Figure 9: Dimensionless velocity magnitude contours for $\phi = 8\%$.

(a) Entire domain.

(b) Detailed view of the vortex breakdown with velocity vectors.

Figure 10: Streamlines for $S = 0.83$, $\phi = 8\%$ and $H/D = 2$.

(a) Entire domain.

(b) Detailed view of the vortex breakdown with velocity vectors.

Figure 11: Streamlines for $S = 0.83$, $\phi = 8\%$ and $H/D = 4$.

295 (e) and (f), which is also plotted in solid line in Figs. 10 and 11, for $H/D = 2$ and
 296 $H/D = 4$, respectively. Streamlines outside the vortex breakdown bubble are plotted
 297 in dashed line. As discussed by other authors [53], the heat transfer in the center of
 298 the plate is strongly diminished as a consequence of this bubble. According to [59],
 299 this is due to the low velocity at which this recirculation occurs. The bubble becomes,

300 curiously, smaller for greater H/D values. This agrees with results reported by [53].

Figure 12: Nusselt profiles on the plate for different nozzle-to-plate distances and swirl intensities, but only one volume fraction, $\phi = 4\%$.

301 The uniformity of the heat transfer, in terms of the standard deviation, is shown
 302 in Fig. 7 (c). The higher the standard deviation, the less uniform the heat transfer.
 303 The value of σ is evaluated by using the Nusselt profile along the plate, as shown in
 304 Fig. 12. According to Fig. 7 (c), the addition of nanoparticles yields a less uniform
 305 heat transfer (σ increases). The increase of the swirl also worsens the heat transfer,
 306 because of the presence of the vortex breakdown bubble (see Fig. 12). Moreover, this
 307 is worsened for smaller nozzle-to-plate separations when $S > 0$. For $S = 0$, the lower
 308 the separation the best the uniformity (i.e. a lower σ value).

309 As said, the heat transfer becomes less uniform as the swirl number increases. This
 310 result is directly related to the existence of two peaks for non-swirling jet and a single
 311 peak for swirling flows in Fig. 12. The secondary peak in Nusselt profiles has been
 312 observed by many authors [53, 18, 1, 59, 19] but there is not yet a clear universal
 313 accepted explanation. Still, some authors [53, 60] attribute this to the increase in
 314 turbulence intensity. Specifically, in [12, 61, 19, 18] it is pointed out that the secondary
 315 peak is consequence of the transition to turbulence of the wall jet boundary layer. As S
 316 increases, the peak is shifted radially outwards so the the standard deviation increases.
 317 The nozzle-to-plate distance is also relevant since, as observed in [12], the potential core
 318 of the jet impinging on the heated surface may cause these secondary peak appearances.
 319 Generally speaking, for high separations, the potential core end is above the stagnation

320 point, which may be linked to the disappearance, or decrease, of the secondary peak.
 321 In our case, for $H/D = 4$ the peak still appears so, as suggested in [61], it may be
 322 because at this distance the plate remains in the area of influence of the potential core.
 323 On the other hand, the vortex breakdown also influences the uniformity of the Nusselt
 324 profiles. In [62] it is remarked that uniformity fades away when the bubble appears,
 325 which agrees with results shown in Fig. 7(c), where the greatest deviation is given for
 326 $S = 0.83$ and $H/D = 2$, in which the bubble is the largest. To clarify the dependence
 327 of output parameters on S , in Fig. 13 is depicted the variation of the three quantities
 328 of interest (Nu_0 , \overline{Nu} and σ) with S for a constant volume fraction of $\phi = 6\%$. One can
 329 observe again that, in general, \overline{Nu} and σ increase and Nu_0 decreases as S increases.

Figure 13: Output parameters with respect to S for the indicated nozzle-to-plate distances and $\phi = 6\%$.

330 An additional objective in this paper is to provide correlations for heat transfer
 331 predictions [54]. The proposed correlations relate, for each nozzle-to-plate distance
 332 H/D , the magnitudes of interest with the swirl intensity S and the Prandtl number of
 333 the nanofluid, which depends on the considered volume fraction of nanoparticles ϕ ; and
 334 therefore the Prandtl number of the nanofluid Pr_{nf} . These models have the same terms

335 for each H/D value, but different values of the coefficients. The correlation models have
 336 the form:

$$f = a \cdot (1 \pm S^b) \cdot Pr_{nf}^c + d, \quad (17)$$

337 where f can be any of the output parameters of interest, i.e. \overline{Nu} , Nu_0 or σ , while a ,
 338 b , c and d are fitting constants. The “+” sign is for \overline{Nu} and σ , and the “-” sign is
 339 for Nu_0 . The sign is due parameter dependence on S : as seen in Fig. 13, \overline{Nu} and σ
 340 increase, mainly as S increases (positive sign), whereas Nu_0 decreases as S increases
 341 (negative sign). The range of validity of the input parameters is $S \in [0, 0.83]$ and
 342 $Pr_{nf} \in [7, \sim 14]$. As aforementioned, the fitting constants a, b, c and d of Eq. (17)
 343 have a specific value depending on the quantity of interest and the H/D value, as can
 344 be seen in Table 3. The relative error between the numerical values and correlation
 345 values is calculated by

$$error \text{ [\%]} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{|num_i - corr_i|}{num_i} \right) \cdot 100, \quad (18)$$

346 where N is the number of training points, num_i is the i -th numerical value and $corr_i$ is
 347 the i -th value predicted by the correlation. Fig. 14 illustrates the goodness of each fit by
 348 plotting the 5% error bands. Moreover, a comparison between the numerical values and
 349 those predicted by Eq. (17) is shown in the figure for each output quantity of interest.
 350 It can be seen that, most predictions lie within the error bands. This, together with
 351 the $error$ and the R^2 as goodness of fit in Table 3 show that the proposed correlations
 352 are accurate.

353 5. Conclusions

354 In the present study the cooling of surfaces by the application of a turbulent
 355 swirling/non-swirling impinging jet of nanofluids has been studied numerically. In this
 356 cooling process, the volume fraction of nanoparticles, the swirl intensity and the nozzle-
 357 to-plate distance have been varied in order to analyze the influence of these parameters

		Fitting constants					
	f	a	b	c	d	$error$ [%]	R^2
$H/D = 2$	\overline{Nu}	30.569	1.9416	0.66291	207.52	0.7813	0.994
	Nu_0	195.23	1.1334	0.2714	25.6733	0.8072	0.99
	σ	135.7	1.5112	0.15691	-142.01	2.5112	0.998
$H/D = 4$	\overline{Nu}	107.6984	18.7539	0.4179	93.2282	1.5589	0.998
	Nu_0	418.7475	4.6251	0.1859	-174.2732	1.549	0.998
	σ	12.029	0.57874	0.50911	35.526	0.8497	0.996

Table 3: Fitting constant values for the correlations depending on H/D values.

358 on the applied heat transfer system performance, quantified by the area-weighted aver-
359 age Nusselt number, the Nusselt number at the stagnation point and the heat transfer
360 uniformity.

361 The results of the present application outline that the heat transfer at the stagnation
362 point is worsened with increasing swirl number and with decreasing nozzle-to-plate
363 separation, due to jet widening and radial deviation of the flow as it impinges on the
364 plate. In addition, for high swirl intensity jets this decrease in the heat transfer is
365 even more noticeable as a consequence of the observed vortex breakdown. The cooling
366 process, on average, increases with increasing swirl number for small nozzle-to-plate
367 distances, but decreases with increasing the swirl number for high H/D distances.
368 Regarding the uniformity of the surface cooling, it has been observed that it decreases
369 with increasing swirl number, and this is strongly related to the presence of peaks in the
370 Nusselt profile. The increase in the fraction of nanoparticles enhances the heat transfer
371 in all the tested configurations.

372 Regarding the optimal configurations for the application under study, the maximum
373 averaged heat transfer was observed for $S = 0.83$ and $H/D = 2$, whereas the maximum
374 value at the stagnation point takes place for $S = 0$ and $H/D = 4$. The maximum
375 level of uniformity was reached at $S = 0.83$ and $H/D = 2$. Additionally, all these
376 maximum values are obtained for the highest volume fraction of nanoparticles under

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 14: Confrontation between numerical results and correlation values for (a) \overline{Nu} , (b) Nu_0 and (c) σ .

377 consideration, $\phi = 10\%$. Moreover, different correlations have been proposed to predict
 378 the three quantities of interest, i.e. \overline{Nu} , Nu_0 and σ , as function of the three input
 379 parameters, i.e. S , H/D and ϕ (by means of Pr_{nf}).

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